

PREPARATION OF SULPHONES AND SULPHOXIDES OF SOME AROMATIC HYDROXYKETONES

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Oxidation of 2 : 2'-dihydroxy-3 : 3'-dimethyl-5 : 5'-diacetyl-, 2 : 2'-dihydroxy-3 : 3'-diacetyl-5 : 5'-dimethyl-, 3 : 3'-diacetyl-4 : 4'-dihydroxy-6 : 6'-dimethyl- and 3 : 3'-diacetyl-4 : 4'-dimethyl-6 : 6'-dihydroxy-diphenyl sulphides with hydrogen peroxide in acetone solution furnished the corresponding sulphones.

Interaction of thionyl chloride and 3-methyl-4-hydroxy-, 2-hydroxy-5-methyl-, 2-hydroxy-4-methyl- and 2-methyl-4-hydroxy-acetophenones in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride yielded the corresponding sulphoxides.

Among the various oxidising agents known to oxidise sulphides to sulphones, hydrogen peroxide is found to be the best, as it does not attack, in presence of a solvent, groups other than sulphide; further, the isolation of the product is also easy. In the present work, oxidation was therefore carried out by means of hydrogen peroxide in presence of acetone. The oxidation products are assigned the constitution of sulphones, as they differ from the substances obtained by the action of thionyl chloride on aromatic hydroxyketones in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride, when sulphoxides are obtained. It has been proved by Smiles and his co-workers that interaction of thionyl chloride and phenol and *p*-cresol in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride furnishes sulphoxides (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1907, 91, 1118; 1910, 97, 2249). Hence, the products obtained in thionyl chloride reaction have been assigned the sulphoxide constitution.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

The sulphide (1 g.) was dissolved in acetone (30 c.c.) and hydrogen peroxide (20 c.c., 100 vols.) was added to it. The mixture was well shaken, taking care to see that the sulphide remained in solution (more acetone being added, if necessary). The mixture was left overnight at room temperature. Usually the oxidation product separated in a crystalline form. It was filtered and washed with acetone yield 0.8 g. (approx.) in all cases. The results are described in Table I.

TABLE I

Sulphones (C₁₈H₁₈O₆S) obtained from corresponding sulphides (C₁₈H₁₈O₄S) through oxidation.

No.	Diphenyl sulphides.	M.P. of sulphones.	% Sulphur (found) *
1.	2 : 2'-Dihydroxy-3 : 3'-dimethyl-5 : 5'-diacetyl-	212-113°	8.92
2.	2 : 2'-Dihydroxy-3 : 3'-diacetyl-5 : 5'-dimethyl-	222-23°	8.68
3.	3 : 3'-Diacetyl-4 : 4'-dihydroxy-6 : 6'-dimethyl-	260-61°	8.96
4.	3 : 3'-Diacetyl-4 : 4'-dimethyl-6 : 6'-dihydroxy-	159-60°	8.52

* C₁₈H₁₈O₆S requires S, 8.84%.

Anhydrous aluminium chloride (4 g.) was dissolved in dry nitrobenzene (30 c.c.) and the requisite ketone (5 g.) was added to it. The mixture was allowed to cool to room temperature and then thionyl chloride (2.5 c.c.) was added and the whole mixture was allowed to stand for 24 hours. Usually the reaction mixture changed colour. The mixture was then poured into hydrochloric acid and nitrobenzene was removed. The residue was crystallised from a suitable solvent. With H_2SO_4 (conc.) sulphoxides (1) and (4) developed dark violet coloration, (2) gave red coloration and (3) gave a dark green coloration. These colours disappeared on addition of phenol. The results are described in Table II.

TABLE II

No.	Acetophenones.	Corresponding diphenyl sulphoxide.	Cryst. from.	M.P.	Yield.	Mol. formula	Found.
1.	3-Methyl-4-hydroxy-	2 : 2'-Dihydroxy-3 : 3'-dimethyl-5 : 5'-diacetyl-	Benzene	158-69°	2 g.	$C_{18}H_{18}O_5S$	C, 62.23; H, 5.28; S, 9.15.
2.	2-Hydroxy-5-methyl-	2 : 2'-Dihydroxy-3 : 3'-diacetyl-5 : 5'-dimethyl-	Acetic acid	260-61° (decomp.)	2	$C_{18}H_{18}O_5S$	C, 62.08; H, 5.17; S, 8.93.
3.	2-Hydroxy-4-methyl-	3 : 3'-Diacetyl-4 : 4'-dihydroxy-6 : 6'-dimethyl-	EtOH	120° (decomp.)	1	$C_{18}H_{18}O_5S$	C, 62.14; H, 5.01; S, 9.14.
4.	4-Hydroxy-2-methyl*	3 : 3'-Diacetyl-4 : 4'-dimethyl-5 : 6'-dihydroxy- or 3 : 3'-Diacetyl-2 : 2'-dimethyl-6 : 6'-dihydroxy-	$CHCl_3$	228-29°	1	$C_{18}H_{18}O_5S$	C, 62.07; H, 5.3; S, 9.15.
							$C_{18}H_{18}O_5S$ requires C. 62.43; H, 5.2; S, 9.24%.

*Reaction mixture was kept at 0° instead at room temperature.